

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF FURANO COMPOUNDS
PART X. 2-PHENYLCOUMARONES

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A simple method of preparation of 2-phenylcoumarones from *o*-methoxybenzyl aryl ketones of the type (I) is described.

A remarkably simple method of preparation of 2-phenylcoumarone (II: R=Ph) in an excellent yield has been achieved by boiling α -cyano- α -(*o*-methoxyphenyl)-acetophenone (I: R=Ph) with hydrobromic acid in acetic acid. This involves completion of four stages, viz., hydrolysis, decarboxylation, demethylation and cyclisation, in one operation.

Several 2-phenylcoumarones have been prepared by this simple procedure; these are collectively described in Table Ib. 2-Benzylcoumarone (Stoermer *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 72) has been prepared similarly from the cyano-ketone (I: R=PhCH₂). When the compound (I: R=2-OMe.C₆H₄) was similarly treated with hydrobromic acid, the product was a mixture of 2-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-coumarone and the furo-coumarin (III). The latter has the same skeleton as tri-*o*-methylwedelolactone, a natural product derivative (Govindachari *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 629).

In an attempt to prepare 2-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-coumarone, required in another investigation, the keto-nitrile (I: R = 2-ethoxycarbonylphenyl) was prepared from *o*-methoxyphenylacetone nitrile and ethyl phthalate. The required coumarone was, however, not obtained from it by this method, possibly because of the facile formation of the phthalide (IV), which has been isolated.

EXPERIMENTAL *

2-Phenylcoumarone.—A mixture of the cyano-ketone (I: R=Ph; Chatterjea, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 447) (0.6 g.), acetic acid (7 c.c.) and hydrobromic acid (7 c.c., 48%) was heated in an oil-bath* (150-60°) for 3 hours. The mixture was poured into water and the precipitated 2-phenylcoumarone (0.4 g.) crystallised from alcohol. The com-

* All m.p.s are uncorrected.

pound was obtained in colorless plates, m.p. 120-21° (lit., m.p. 120°). (Found: C, 87.0; H, 5.2. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}O$: C, 86.6; H, 5.2%). The compound dissolved in sulphuric acid with a yellow colour which turned green immediately.

2-Benzylcoumarone.—A solution of *o*-methoxyphenylacetonitrile (4.4 g. Baker *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1386) and ethyl phenylacetate (5.0 g.) in benzene (20 c.c.) was added to dry sodium ethoxide (sodium, 0.7 g.) and refluxed for 2 hours. The *sodium salt* of the keto-nitrile (I: R=PhCH₂) (6.9 g.) separating was collected, washed with dry ether, dissolved in water and acidified. The *keto-nitrile* was obtained in colorless prisms from methanol, m.p. 96°. (Found: C, 77.4; H, 5.7. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 76.9; H, 5.7%). This nitrile (2.0 g.) was refluxed for 9 hours with a mixture of acetic acid (20 c.c.) and HBr (20 c.c.). The product, isolated with ether, was washed with alkali, dried and distilled. *2-Benzylcoumarone* was obtained as a colorless oil (1.2 g.), b.p. 174°/8.5 mm. (Stoermer *et al.*, record b.p. 180-85°/15 mm). (Found: C, 86.4; H, 5.6. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{14}O$: C, 86.5; H, 5.8%). The compound gave a pink coloration with sulphuric acid.

Benzofuro-(2':3':4)-coumarin.—Equimolecular quantities of *o*-methoxyphenylacetonitrile and ethyl *o*-methoxybenzoate were refluxed in dry benzene solution with freshly prepared sodium ethoxide (1 M) for 5 hours. The *keto-nitrile* (I: R=2-OMe.C₆H₄) crystallised from alcohol in colorless prisms, m.p. 112°. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 5.3; N, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N$ requires C, 72.6; H, 5.3; N, 5.0%). The nitrile (1.7 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of acetic acid (9 c.c.) and HBr (9 c.c.) for 3 hours. The mixture was poured into water and cooled overnight in a refrigerator. The solid on crystallisation from acetic acid gave the *furo-coumarin* (III) in bluish prismatic needles, m.p. 180-81°, yield 0.15 g. (Found: C, 76.1; H, 3.5. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 76.2; H, 3.3%).

The compound responds to no ferric reaction and is insoluble in dilute alkali. The acetic acid mother-liquor was treated with water and the precipitated product extracted with dilute alkali, filtered and acidified. *2-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl)-coumarone* was obtained in colorless prisms from acetic acid, m.p. 95°, developing a green coloration with H₂SO₄. (Found: C, 80.2; H, 5.0. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 4.8%).

Condensation of Ethyl Phthalate with o-Methoxyphenylacetonitrile.—Ethyl phthalate (4.4 g.) was condensed with the nitrile (3.0 g.) in the presence of dry sodium ethoxide (sodium, 0.47 g.) as before. The resulting *keto-nitrile* (I: R=2-ethoxycarbonylphenyl) which had no tendency to crystallise was boiled with a mixture of acetic acid and HBr (10 c.c. each) for 8 minutes. The gummy product, obtained on pouring into water, solidified in contact with alcohol. The *phthalide* (IV) on two crystallisations from alcohol was obtained in golden yellow flat needles, m.p. 159-60°, dissolving in sulphuric acid with a light colour. [Found: C, 73.7, 73.7; H, 4.0, 4.0; N, 5.3; OMe, 10.7. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 73.6; H, 4.0; N, 5.1; OMe (1), 11.2%].

In Table IA are described some of the keto-nitriles obtained by the condensation of *o*-methoxyphenylacetonitrile with substituted benzoic-esters and the 2-phenylcoumarones derived from these nitriles are shown in Table IB.

TABLE I

No.	Substituent.	Solvent of cryst.	Cryst. shape.	Yield.	M.P.	Mol. formula.	Found.	Calc.
A. Keto-nitriles (I).								
1.	R = C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Acetic acid-alcohol	Colorless prisms	70%	109-10°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	N: 5.2%	5.3%
2.	R = C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	Acetic acid	Do	68	71-72°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	N: 5.0	5.3
3.	R = C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Acetic acid	Do	60	123-24°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	N: 5.0	5.3
4.	R = C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>p</i>)	Do	Do	70	111-12°	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₂ NCl	N: 4.8	4.7
5.	R = C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Alcohol	Do	68	106°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N	N: 5.2	5.0
B. 2-Phenylcoumarones (II)								
1.	R = C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	Alcohol	Colorless plates	85	127-28°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O	C: 86.0 H: 5.5	86.5; 5.8
2.	R = C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>m</i>)	Do	Colorless prisms	75	78-80°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O	C: 86.0 H: 5.7	86.5; 5.8
3.	R = C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (<i>o</i>)	Methanol	Do	15*	98°	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O	C: 86.1 H: 6.0	86.5; 5.8
4.	R = C ₆ H ₄ Cl (<i>p</i>)	Acetic acid	Colorless plates	80	149°	C ₁₄ H ₉ OCl	C: 73.1 H: 4.0	73.5 3.9:
5.	R = C ₆ H ₄ OH (<i>p</i>)	Do	Colorless prisms	60	192°	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂	C: 80.3 H: 5.3	80.0; 4.8

* The compound failed to crystallise completely

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